

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

System prototypes report

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For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

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Executive summary

The scope of this report is to describe the prototype system developed on the basis of the guidelines described in the system design document. The report shows the solutions produced and some improvements with respect to the designed solution (see deliverable D2.1) and preliminary results in each of the system layers (hardware, service and communication layer). The document presents the state of the art of the 4onse environmental monitoring system prototype which is ready to be sent to the testing partners. It provides detailed information on data accuracy, hardware durability, manual instruction accessibility and general quality, reproducibility of the system.

1 Introduction

The 4onse project aims to build a non-conventional Environmental Monitoring System (EMS) based on open hardware, software, standards and data to monitor droughts, floods and manage the water resources. To this end, a system prototype has been designed (deliverable 2.1, system design report) and then developed and preliminary tested. It is composed by three interconnected parts: hardware, service and communication layers. Each layer plays a key role in the whole chain and is strictly connected to the others. The weather station (hardware layer) provides climatic observations of the most important environmental parameters including the water river level which will be used in the future steps of the project for hydrological models and studies. The data measured are archived into a data management system (service layer) based on the istSOS software which is OGC SOS compliant. An in depth analysis of the istSOS's performances showed some limitations in supporting Big-Data, thus a new software, istSOS-proxy, has been developed in this phase to offer the possibility to scale over big datasets and many concurrent users. The communication layer is the link between the other two layers. A fast communication method together with a strategy to prevent data loss have been implemented and evaluated to offer a robust and consistent data transmission according to the requirements listed in the System Design report (project deliverable D2.1).

This report is divided in three parts. The first part illustrates the implemented system for each layer in terms of methods and material used. The second part presents the results of a first evaluation performed to validate the prototypes and the taken strategies. The last part, synthesizes the main outputs produced and comments on the general system prototype including an evaluation of the whole developed chain.

2 Material and Methods

This chapter illustrates the project approach used for the implementation of the 4onse prototype system; for each of the three layers the applied methods are presented.

2.1 Hardware layer

The hardware layer of the prototype system has been implemented following the design reported in the "System design report". In order to fulfil the individuated requirements, the project team has decided to implement two prototype solutions of the system composed by the same hardware components but with different integration strategies (with power supply and microcontroller). As a consequence, this report presents both the developed solutions: the 4onse modular prototype (4onse-mod) and the 4onse Printed Circuit Board prototype (4onse-pcb).

4onse-mod: modular solution prototype

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

The general installation schema of the 4onse-mod solution is illustrated in the Figure 1. A central pole sustains the box container, where the unit controller is installed, and the sensors that, due to best practice guidelines, must be placed at appropriate distance from the ground and surrounding buildings or other obstacles.

Figure 1 – Weather station general schema.

The hardware components and the sensors have been classified in parts inside the box container (Table 1) and outside the box container (Table 2).

Name	Description
Arduino MEGA 2560 (2)	The microcontroller board which works as the core of the system. It manages the communication, read values from the sensors and log them into the data logger.
SIM800 (1)	The GPRS module which is used to transmit the data to the server.
DS3231 (3)	The RTC to get the date and time values.
OpenLog (4)	The SD card interface to keep track of the sensor data.
LM393 (6)	The adapter comparator connected to the soil moisture sensor.
DHT11 (5)	The temperature and humidity sensor to monitor the internal state. 5% accuracy for 20-80% humidity readings and $\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ accuracy for 0-50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ temperature readings.
Step-down converter	The step-down converter is used to convert the voltage from 12V to 7V and 5V.

Table 1 - List of the components inside the box container.

Name	Description
DS18B20 (6)	The external waterproof sensor used to measure the air temperature. It reports degrees from -55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 125 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with an

	accuracy of +/-0.5°C and a resolution of 0.0625°C.
BME280 (5)	It gives air pressure and humidity values respectively with an accuracy of ± 1 hPa and ± 3 % and resolution of 0.18 Pa and 0.008 %.
Davis AeroCone 6465	The rain gauge has a resolution of 0.2 mm and a collection area of 214 cm ² .
Anemometer (1-4)	This sensor is composed by a wind direction and speed plastic sensors.
YL-69 (3)	The soil moisture sensor can read the amount of water present in the soil surrounding it.
BH1750 (2)	It is a digital light sensor which provides lux with high resolution values.

Table 2 - List of the components outside the box container.

Figure 2 – Main components inside the box on the left and outside of the box on the right (rain gauge is not depicted).

The 4nse-mod solution tries to maximize the reproducibility of the system, using as much as possible common materials (devices, box, screws, etc.). It is based on a Plexiglas board that host on the back-side the power regulation controls and on the front-side all the other

components (Figure 3). This choice has been made to facilitate the sensor replacements, hiding as much as possible connection cable from the user interaction side.

The back-side can be divided into two main parts. The first, at the bottom-left of the board, is composed by two step-down converters powered up by a 12V current and used to provide the right voltage to the Arduino board and to the rest of the components respectively with 7V (suggested input voltage by the Arduino datasheet) and 5V. The second part is characterized by a terminal barrier block at the top of the board which is useful to split the 5V current and to prepare the cables and power up all the other components.

The front-side is organized with the Arduino core component placed at the centre of the board. Then, the other internal hardware devices are positioned around. A terminal barrier block is fixed at the bottom of the board to work as the main connection interface between the Arduino and the external sensors.

The plexi set-up with the devices can be easily mounted inside a plastic box and fixed on the pole with the external sensors.

Figure 3 – Front and back side schema of the first weather station prototype. The cables drawn brings power to the hardware devices.

The Figure 4 shows the entire system built and tested at the SUSPSI - Institute of Science Erath in Canobbio (Switzerland). The station can be powered up by a 12V current provided by a solar system or wired system.

Figure 4 - The 4nse-mod station.

4nse-pcb: Printed Circuit Board solution prototype

(B.H. Sudantha, Emeshi Warusavitharana, Sandaru Weerasinghe, Dananjaya Bandara)

The 4nse-pcb comes with two stations – a main station and a river gauge. The main station measures all the aforesaid environmental parameters except the water level. The water level is measured by the river station.

The weather station was developed as an Arduino Mega2560 based embedded system. All the sensors except river gauge are directly connected with the main system. The river gauge was separately developed using Arduino UNO and necessary electronic modules, in order to keep distance between the main system and river gauge. The communication between the main system and the river gauge was established using wireless technologies. All the processing and controlling were carried out by Arduino Mega2560 and all the data collected at the station is sent to main server using GSM technology. Figure 5 shows the block diagram of the 4nse main system architecture.

The key features of the system are:

- The entire system with the river gauge can be built at a cost of 725.13 USD.
- Portable system
- Easy installation - Since there are separate boxes in to carry the main processing unit, power supply unit and the sensor unit, it is easy to install and maintain.
- Sensors can be easily added – Additional sensors can be added to the sensor connection panel and each sensor has its own dedicated socket to plug in.
- Use renewable energy source – The selected study area to deploy the 4nse system is Deduru Oya basin of Sri Lanka. A predominant part of the basin area belongs to rural sector, where the electricity coverage is limited. Hence the system is powered by 25Ah battery and 30W solar panel. This battery can run the system more than 3 days.

- Self-diagnostic system – The system is equipped with internal temperature sensor and voltage monitoring meter. Therefore, the system can continuously monitor the system voltage and temperature. The cooling fan inside the system automatically starts when the internal temperature of the system is higher than 37°C.
- Weather readings can be viewed through the real-time display and the detailed weather conditions may be viewed at any distance over the internet.
- Soldered PCB – The PCB of the system comes as a soldered unit which includes sections for all the main circuits and sensors.

Figure 5 - Block diagram of the 4nse main system architecture.

The system comprises of main processing and controlling system with Arduino Mega2560, power supply unit and several sensors. The Mega2560 receives readings from all sensors and it carries out the processing of readings. It sends data to the server using a GSM module. The power supply section consists of 30W solar panel, 25Ah sealed lead acid battery, solar charging controller and several regulators to supply different voltages to several sections of the system. Sensors are detecting nine parameters including ambient temperature, pressure, light, humidity, wind direction, wind speed, rain level, soil moisture and water level of water bodies. The river gauge is an optional parameter and it is available only for specific weather stations depending on the requirements. The codes used to program the Arduino Mega2560 is available in the following link: <https://github.com/HarithKK/ISTSOS>.

Table 3 shows the components of the main system block and their functions and Figure 6 shows the image of the 4nse main system block. Table 4 shows the components of the power supply section and their functions. Table 5 shows the sensors used in the system and their functions.

Component	Functions
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4onse main controlling and processing unit	Contains mainly the main controller - Arduino Mega2560, SD module, RTC – DS1307, GSM module – SIM800, Relay module, Power regulators and other necessary electronic components.
16 x 2 Alphanumeric LCD	Displays the data in weather station locally
12V DC brushless Fan	Removes excessive heat of the main system block
Printed Circuit Board (PCB)	Connects all the components of the weather station

Table 3 - Components of the main system block.

Component	Functions
100W Solar Charger	Converts the solar energy to voltage
30W Solar panel	Controls solar panel voltage and provides the charging voltage to the battery
12V, 25Ah rechargeable battery	Stores solar energy and provides power to the system
LM338K DC voltage regulator	Regulates the battery voltage to GSM module and Mega2560
LM7805 DC voltage regulators	Provides the necessary supply voltages to sensors, other modules and system fan
DC step-up voltage regulator	Provides a boost voltage to wind speed and wind direction sensors

Table 4 - Components of the power supply section.

Name of the sensor	Measured Parameters
DS18B20 sensor	To measure the temperature
BH1750 light sensor module	To measure the light intensity
4onse soil moisture module	To measure the soil moisture
BME280 sensor	To measure atmospheric pressure and humidity
ZHIPU wind speed sensor	To measure the wind speed
Anemometer 485 Wind direction sensor	To measure the wind direction
Davis AeroCone Rain Collector (Product number 6465)	To measure the rainfall

4onse river gauge module	To measure the water level
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Table 5 - Sensors of the sensor unit and their measured parameters.

Figure 6 - Main system block.

The circuit design of the system

The 4onse-pcb's main system consists of a main controller, many supporting modules and several sensors. Figure 7 shows the schematic diagram of the main system. The main controller of the system is Arduino Mega2560 and its primary functions are collecting data from all the sensors, processing some of the data before sending them to the server, controlling and communicating other peripherals including SD module, real time clock module (RTC), fan controller and GSM module. Upon receiving all the data from all the sensors, it will send the data to the server with 15 minutes time interval.

Figure 7 - Schematic diagram of the 4nse main system.

Internal temperature and battery voltages are being monitored in order to ensure the proper operation of the system. When the internal temperature is exceeded the threshold value of 37°C, the internal DC fan will be turned on to remove the internal hot air of the main system box. The battery voltage would be monitored and recorded to be used in the error tracking process, with it functions such as solar panel power receiving cycle, battery power storing capabilities could be monitored. Also power saving mechanism may be turned on if the battery power is getting down.

In the initial start-up of the system, SIM800 module is not powered up. Therefore, the module will be turned on by activating the soft power ON facility of the module. For every start-up, the mega main controller will enable the power ON function of the SIM800 by using a transistor switching circuit.

Furthermore, two indicators are fixed in the box, enabling users to check the availability of power and status of the GSM module. If the GSM status indicator does not turn on intermittently, it indicates that an error on GSM module operations and no communication is going on. The LCD back light is also turned on via a push ON switch, if the user needs to turn on backlight, it can be done using the push-on button and it lasts only for the key pressed duration. This modification was done in order to stop unnecessary illumination of LCD and to save power.

Main power section includes solar power/charge controller, solar panel and lead-acid sealed type battery. Under normal circumstances, 12V is received from the charge controller and sometimes, when the battery is fully charged, the supply voltage is increased in the range of 12.0 to 13.6 V. Although Mega and GSM modules are equipped with voltage regulators, the

higher voltages more than 12 V is not good for both devices (Refer the datasheet of Mega2560). Considering the safety of both modules, a linear regulator LM338K was used to regulate the supply voltage to the main circuit. Also, another two 7805 linear local regulators were used to provide power to sensors and modules and to fan controller in order to reduce the noise disturbances and power fluctuations.

The Printed Circuit Board of the system

The main Printed Circuit Board (PCB) was designed including all the circuit modifications of the main system. The first version of the PCB was designed incorporating all the signal conditioning, sensors and power modules only. The Mega controller, GSM module, RTC, fan controller and SD modules were separately mounted within the main system box. The first developments of the PCB are shown in Figure 8 to Figure 10. They include the bottom copper, top copper, top silk and mechanical layers.

Figure 8 - All inclusive view of the PCB V1 (top side view of all layers).

Figure 9 - Bottom copper layer of the PCB V2 (bottom copper side view).

Figure 10 - Bottom copper layout layer of the PCB V3 (slightly modified).

All the connections between the PCB and above mentioned modules were made by using jumper wires. This design stage comprised of three boxes as shown in Figure 11, namely main controller box (main processing unit), sensors connectivity box (sensor unit) and power control box (power supply unit). The main controller box contained PCB V3 with wired connection of Mega, GSM, RTC, SD, soil moisture signal conditioning module and fan controller. All the sensors were connected to sensor connectivity box and connection bus with power lines were linked between main box and sensor connectivity box. Figure 12 shows the schematic diagram of sensor connectivity box and Figure 13 shows the PCB design of the sensor panel.

Figure 11 - The block view of the initial stage of 4ONSE system.

Figure 12 - The schematic diagram of the sensor connectivity panel.

Figure 13 - The PCB of the sensor connectivity panel.

Although the system was functioned at the beginning and sent data during the test period to server at www.spliot.org, there were several cases where the system was found to be not performing properly. Some of the problems traced were lack of GSM signals time to time, the connectivity problems between modules and power fluctuation issues, etc. As a practise, in order to reduce the power issues such as power fluctuations due to long wires, noise pickups in different environments and also to maintain signal to noise ratio as possible as below the allowed threshold levels, short wires should be used whenever possible. Therefore, this three box model was modified to two box model by combining both sensor connectivity box and main control box to a single box. Also the design of the PCB was extended to connect all the modules, main controller and sensors to one board removing all the possible jumper wires to enhance the signal quality of the system even in the noisy outside environments. After applying all the modifications considering above mentioned factors,

Figure 14 and

Figure 15 illustrate the all-inclusive view and bottom copper layer of the final version of the PCB which is used in the current development of the system respectively. Figure 16 shows the final block diagram of the 4nse main station. Figure 17 and Figure 18 shows the main system board based on the final PCB and its rear image respectively. Figure 19 shows the final version of the of the 4nse-pcb system.

Figure 14 - All-inclusive layers view of the final version of the PCB (top view).

Figure 15 - Bottom copper layer of final PCB (top view).

Figure 16 - The block view of the final stage of 4nse main station.

Figure 17 - Main system board based on the final PCB.

Figure 18 - Rear image of the final PCB.

Figure 19 - The final version of the 4nse system.

Wind speed – ZHIPU sensor

ZHIPU and SEN-08942 sensors were compared prior to the selection of ZHIPU sensor to measure the wind speed (Table 6).

	ZHIPU Sensor	SEN-08942
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Range	0- 32.4m/s	na
Accuracy	5%	10%
Resolution	0.2-0.4m/s	0.6m/s
Opertion Voltage	15 V	10V

Table 6- Comparison of ZHIPU and SEN-08942 sensors.

Compared to the SEN-08942, ZHIPU sensor has better accuracy and resolution. The cost factor was not compared in the above table, since the SEN-08942 sensor comes with three components of weather measurement: wind speed, wind direction and rainfall, while the ZHIPU sensor comes only with one component of weather measurement: wind speed. Further ZHIPU wind speed sensor is ideal for tropical country like Sri Lanka due to the following features:

- The sensor is made up of Aluminum Alloy material. Hence it is high in strength
- Weather resistance
- Anti-corrosion
- Water resistance

The supply voltage of the sensor is 12V – 24V which is out of the available power of the system. Therefore, additional power regulator was used to step up the supply voltage of the sensor. Since the sensor is light in weights, it is more suitable for a mobile weather station.

The interfacing methodology of the wind speed sensor to the main controlling block is illustrated in Figure 21.

Figure 20 - ZHIPU wind speed sensor.

Figure 21 - Block diagram of interfacing ZHIPU wind speed sensor.

Wind direction – Anemometer 485 sensor

Anemometer 485 and SEN-08942 sensors were compared prior to the selection of Anemometer 485 sensor to measure the wind direction (Table 7).

Figure 22 - Wind direction sensor.

	Anemometer 485	SEN-08942
Range	0-360 degrees (16 directions)	0-360 degrees (16 directions)
Accuracy	5%	10%
Resolution	22.5 degrees	22.5 degrees
Operation Voltage	12 V – 24V	10V

Table 7 - Comparison of Anemometer 485 and SEN-08942 sensors.

Compared to SEN-08942, Anemometer 485 has better accuracy. The cost factor was not compared in the above table, since the SEN-08942 sensor comes with three components of weather measurement: wind speed, wind direction and rainfall, while the Anemometer 485 comes only with one component of weather measurement: wind direction. Further, Anemometer 485 is made up of metal and SEN-08942 is made up of plastic. Hence, in terms of durability, Anemometer 485 is better than SEN-08942.

The supply voltage of Anemometer 485 is 12V – 24V. Therefore, additional power regulator was used to step up the supply voltage for the sensor. The interfacing modules of the sensor is shown in Figure 23. The sensor is more suitable to use in the 4nse due to the following features:

- Capable of measuring 16 directions
- Low power consumption
- Environmental protection and energy saving design
- Convenient to carry and install in the field since the sensor is small in size and light in weight

Figure 23 - Block diagram of interfacing of wind direction.

Soil moisture sensor

During the designing stage of the weather station, a commercially available low cost soil moisture sensor was used. Figure 24, shows the previously used sensor. However, it was

getting corroded () with the time and consequently the resultant readings were received with an incremental error. Figure 26 and Figure 27 show the original calibration curve and the calibration curve received after one month time respectively. Therefore, a new type of soil moisture was designed using stainless steel tubes (Figure 28). Figure 29 shows the calibration curve related to newly developed stainless steel soil moisture sensor. The cost of the new sensor is nearly 5.19 USD and does not have any corrosion problem.

Figure 24 - Commercially available soil moisture sensor.

Figure 25 - (a) Soil moisture sensor (b) Corroded soil moisture sensor.

Figure 26 - Calibration curve of the available soil moisture sensor.

Figure 27 - Calibration curve of the available soil moisture sensor (nearly after one month time).

Figure 28 - Soil moisture sensor developed using stainless steel tubes.

Figure 29 - Calibration curve of the developed stainless steel soil moisture sensor. *Note: In this graph, the initial curve and the after 1 month curve overlap on each other.*

The river gauge

The 4onse-pcb river gauge comes as an independent unit to the system which has a separate mini processing unit with Arduino UNO board. The power supply unit of the river gauge is composed of 10W solar panel, 100W solar charger, 12V and 7Ah rechargeable battery. This mini unit also equipped with a radio transmitter to communicate with the main system. Table 8 shows the components of the 4onse river gauge.

Component	Functions
River gauge controller	Contains Arduino UNO, HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor, RF transceiver
10W Solar panel	Controls solar panel voltage and provides the charging voltage to the battery

100W Solar charger	Converts the solar energy to voltage
12V, 7Ah rechargeable Battery	Stores solar energy and provides power to the system
125mm diameter and 4m height PVC tube	To mount the river gauge controller unit

Table 8 - Components of the 4nse river gauge.

The river gauge of the system was developed using a low cost ultrasonic sensor HC-SR04. However, the river gauge cannot be installed near to the 4nse main station because of the nearby water body’s temperature and humidity reading may be different than surrounding environment. Therefore, the weather station and river gauge should be located keeping the distance at least 500m between each other and the water level will be transmitted to the weather station using RF serial transmitters.

The river gauge is comprised ultrasonic sensor HC-RC04, Arduino UNO controller, solar panel of 100 W, 7AH sealed type battery and RF serial transceiver. The implementation block diagram of the river gauge is illustrated in Figure 30. With this implementation, the maximum 4m of water level could be measured. However, according to the Irrigation Department’s requirement, around 7m should be measured.

This can be improved by using two river gauges one after another or using a different high quality ultrasonic sensor. Figure 33 shows the real implementation of the river gauge at Bolgoda River near to university premises (6.7978°N, 79.9040°E).

Figure 30 - The implementation block diagram of the river gauge.

The communication between the river gauge and the main station was carried out by using two APC220 radio data link devices. Data link was established as serial data communication method using RS232 protocol. Interfacing of APC220 devices to Arduino UNO is very simple like adding another serial communication device. After adding this device to the code, the communication can be done like normal RS232 device.

Although it is mentioned that the range of the device is as 1200 meters in the open space, it was successfully communicated in the open space nearly 600 meters only. However, attaching

a two omni-directional antennas, the extended range up to 800 meters were tested and worked not in the line of sight. Two one meter 5/8" Aluminium tubes were used as two antennas and fixed them to main controller box and river gauge guide tube. Figure 31 shows the image of APC220 RF data link devices and Figure 32 shows how the Arduino UNO, HC-SR04 ultrasonic sensor and APC220 RF data link devices connected together to make the river gauge.

Figure 31 - APC220 RF data transceivers used in the river gauge.

Figure 32 - Arduino UNO, HC-SR04 and APC220 forming the river gauge.

Figure 33 - The river gauge implementation of the 4nse system at 6.7978°N , 79.9040°E.

The power unit

As stated in the 4nse D2.1 System Design Report, Mikhaylov and Tervonen (2011) have pointed out four different power supply options used by network nodes:

- Power supply from electrical grid using AC/DC converters
- Batteries or accumulators
- Energy form environment harvesting system with capacitive storage
- A combination of the above listed options

The 4nse uses 3rd option to supply the power to the system using a 30W solar panel as the environmental energy harvesting system and 12V 25 Ah battery as the capacitive storage. Figure 34 shows the detailed block diagram of the complete power system.

Figure 34 - A detailed block diagram of the complete power system.

The power supply unit is composed of 30W solar panel, 12V 25Ah rechargeable battery, 100W solar panel voltage controller and power regulators to keep voltage in the recommended range of electronic items. The solar panel charges the battery, which is the main power source of the system. It provides 12V direct current to the system. Since 12V is not suitable for ArduinoMega and SIM800 for long run, the power unit has linear voltage regulators to step down the voltage up to 9V. The recommended voltage level for cooling fan and the sensor modules except wind speed and wind direction is 5V. Therefore, the power unit has another two step down regulators for cooling fan and the sensor modules except wind speed and wind direction. The wind speed and wind direction sensors require 15V to operate. Therefore, the power unit is equipped with step up power regulators for these two sensors.

The power unit dimensioning

(B.H. Sudantha, Emeshi Warusavitharana, Sandaru Weerasinghe, Dananjaya Bandara)

Initially, the main power supply of the system was comprised with a 10W solar panel, 12V 7Ah sealed gel battery and a solar panel and charge controller. The system was powered using that system and sometimes it was not enough to power up the system for at least one if the battery was not charged using the sunlight. Theoretically, the following calculation tabulated in Table 9 shows the possible charging cycle per day. Generally, 80% of efficiency could be received from a solar panel.

Theoretical power calculation of previous power system	
Solar panel Wattage	10W
Efficiency of a solar panel	80%
Expected wattage from the panel	$10 \times 0.8 = 8W$
Assumption of full power sunlight	8 hours
Total power from the panel per day	$8 \times 8 = 64 \text{ Wh}$
The capacity of the 12V, 7Ah battery	$12 \times 7 = 84 \text{ Wh}$
Number of days needed to charge the battery fully without providing power to the system	$84 / 64 = 1.3 \text{ days}$
Power calculation based on measured parameters	
Normal average running current of the system without sending data and without cooling fan	0.22 A
Total average current when sending data using SIM900 GSM module without cooling fan	1.2 A
Normal time per day (approximately)	23 hours and 36 minutes
Data sending time (approximately)	24 minutes
Total system required power per day (without cooling fan)	$(12 \times 0.22 \times 23.6) + (12 \times 1.2 \times 0.4)$ $= 62.304 + 5.76$ $= 68.064 \text{ Wh}$

Table 9 - System power calculation theoretical and practical.

Considering the above parameters, it is clear that the system could not be powered up using the power system even if the battery is initially fully charged. All the calculations were carried out based on a primary assumption that the sunlight is available for 8 hours period continuously and the system cooling fan power consumption was also not considered for the calculations. Many changes were incorporated considering the above facts in order to rectify the power supply problems. A 30W solar panel and 25Ah sealed type lead-acid battery were selected instead of previous solar panel and the battery. In addition to that, SIM900 was changed to SIM800 considering the unavailability of the SIM900 and considering the new improvement of the SIM800 chip. It also helps to minimize the total power consumption of the system. Table 10 shows the details of the new system.

Theoretical power calculation of previous power system	
Solar panel Wattage	30W
Efficiency of a solar panel	80%
Expected wattage from the panel	$30 \times 0.8 = 24W$
Assumption of full power sunlight	8 hours
Total power from the panel per day	$24 \times 8 = 192 \text{ Wh}$
The capacity of the 12V, 25Ah battery	$12 \times 25 = 300 \text{ Wh}$
Number of days needed to charge the battery fully without providing power to the system	$300 / 192 = 1.56 \text{ days}$
Power calculation based on measured parameters	
Total average current when sending data using SIM800 GSM module without cooling fan	0.21 A
Total operation time including data sending	24 hours
Total system required power per day (without cooling fan)	$12 \times 0.21 \times 24 = 60.48 \text{ Wh}$
Balance power for charging the battery per day	$192.0 - 60.48 = 131.5 \text{ Wh}$

	(68.48%)
No. of days required to charge battery fully while powering the system	$300 / 131.5 = 2.28$ days

Table 10 - System power calculation theoretical and practical with the current power system.

It is obvious that the system power generation system is fully capable of running the system smoothly with new solar panel and the battery.

The rain gauge calibration

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

The river gauge Davis AeroCone 6465 is factory-calibrated to report 0.2 mm of rain per tip. The shape of this pluviometer is aerodynamically designed to minimize rainfall catch reduction caused by high winds. Thanks to the screws under each chamber the tipping bucket can be accurately tuned and calibrated. For the calibration of the Davis rain gauge, the catchment area and the quantity of rain per tip is needed. Then, a special bottle, which guarantees a low and homogeneous flux of water, filled with a known quantity of water is mounted over the rain gauge. For an acceptable calibration, the quantity of rain measured must have a maximum 5% of error from the referenced and calculated value.

As written above, the Davis rain gauge reports 0.2 mm of rain per tip and has a catchment area of 214 cm². Thus, if 1 mm of rain corresponds to 1 l/m² (100 cl/m²), 1 mm is also equal to 2.14 cl of rain collected by the pluviometer. So, the following relation is true:

$$2.14 \text{ cl} = 1 \text{ mm} = 5 \text{ tips}$$

For the calibration, a bottle with 53.5 cl of water, which is equal to 25 mm of rain and 125 tips, was prepared. The tipping bucket is considered calibrated when the tips measured are between 118.75 and 131.25 (5% error). The calibration has been performed once the weather station was installed, being sure that the body was kept level with the floor.

As shown in Table 11, the rain gauge measures 121 tips instead of 125. On the basis of the previous requirements, the river gauge has been considered calibrated.

Total rain expected	25 mm
Total rain measure	24.2 mm
Total tips expected	125
Total tips measured	121
Acceptable tips range	118.75 - 131.25

Table 11 – Rain gauge calibration results.

2.2 Service layer

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

The service layer is responsible for storing and serving monitored data, which in the modern context of the Internet of Things (IoT) should be able to deal with big data and quality service.

Since the 4ONSE technology selected in System Design phase is the istSOS software, and its capability of supporting these requirements are limited we have implemented a software, named istSOS-proxy, to improve the system capabilities in managing large concurrent requests and big datasets.

The istSOS-proxy

According to the INSPIRE directive 2007/2/EC – regulation (EC) No 976/2009 and to the requirements presented in the “System design report”, the 4onse environmental service layer should provide good performance, capacity and availability. Unfortunately, recent researches has demonstrated that when big datasets meet high requests frequencies, the istSOS software is strongly stressed and its performances degrades so that the requirements of the system are not always assured.

A scalable architecture can substantially increase the capacity of the system to support many concurrent users and massive datasets improving the general performances. Thus, to solve this istSOS performance issue, a lighting fast cascading proxy server, named istSOS-proxy, capable to integrate multiple instances of istSOS has been developed.

This new software component can horizontally scale over distributed databases of time series stored in different istSOS instances in the cloud. It is a unique access point for all the mandatory SOS requests (*GetCapabilities*, *DescribeSensor*, *GetObservation*) that are firstly redirected to the right istSOS instance and then gathered together in a single response.

It is totally developed using Python language and the Tornado web framework (<http://www.tornadoweb.org>) to take advantage of the asynchronous programming and to handle several concurrent users by using the non-blocking network I/O which scales many open connections. istSOS-proxy implements a harvesting mechanism that automatically gathers information from the registered istSOS instances and store it in a local PostgreSQL/PostGIS database for load balancing.

istSOS-proxy is composed by two main services:

- a RESTful service API, to configure the database connection and add istSOS instances;
- SOS service to provide access to sensors metadata and data using the SOS version 1.0.0 and 2.0.0 core profiles.

Figure 35 – Work flow schema illustrating the istSOS-proxy integration with users and istSOS instances.

Load testing configuration

istSOS-proxy aims at improving service performances by distributing time series data over multiple istSOS instances. To evaluate the proposed solution we executed a number of load tests powered by the Locust python tool (<http://locust.io>). During the tests, the general work load over two Virtual Machines (VM) was progressively increased using three levels of users (Strigaro et al., 2017).

Figure 36 – Properties of the istSOS Virtual Machines used for the load testing.

To evaluate the performance of istSOS-proxy we have tested a big dataset over two different configurations: a single istSOS instance (VM-0) where all the data are stored and accessed through a single server and a distributed pattern where the same dataset is divided in two istSOS instances (Figure 36) which are registered, as unique access point, the istSOS-proxy installed on the so called Proxy Machine (PM) (Figure 37).

Figure 37 – istSOS-proxy distributed pattern using a Proxy Machine (PM).

2.3 Communication layer

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

The main activities, carried out within the communication layer, have been focused on the optimization of data transmission from the weather station to the server. Since the standard SOS insertObservation operation, due to its inclusion of metadata and semantic annotations, is verbose and byte eager we have implemented a new transmission method, the *fastInsert*, within the istSOS software. Thanks to this new istSOS method and to the developed Arduino library which implement it, it is now possible to have a fast and light data communication between the hardware layer and the service layer.

The *fastInsert* method

According to the “System design report”, a wireless transmission medium with a GPRS communication protocol are the basis of the development of a new lighter and faster data messaging technology within the istSOS software. This feature enables the data/observations transmission device-to-server by using a RESTful style architecture over HTTP/HTTPS which guarantees a request/response and success/failure patterns.

The Python class, developed and included in the istSOS software to handle the fast insertion of observations, supports only the POST method.

The method requires an header composed as described in Figure 38, where:

- *\$uri* is the path to the *fastInsert* method;
- *\$server* is the base url of the server where istSOS is installed;
- *\$auth* is the basic authentication, composed by the user and the password, encoded in a base64 string;
- *\$data.length()* is the string length of the body/payload.

```
POST $uri HTTP/1.1
Host: $server
Accept: */*
Authorization: Basic $auth
Content-Length: $data.length()
Content-Type: text/plain;charset=utf-8
Connction: keep-alive

$payload
```

Figure 38 - The *fastInsert* header structure.

The body/payload of the request must follow one of the two formats listed below (see Figure 39):

1. a semi-column separated values string composed by four parts:
 - a. the assigned id of the procedure which identifies the weather station;
 - b. the timestamp of the first observation (iso8601 format);
 - c. the time interval between the observations;
 - d. a list, with '@' separated values, composed by comma separated lists of measures
2. a semi-column separated values string composed by two parts:
 - a. the assigned id of the procedure which identifies the weather station;
 - b. a list, with '@' separated values, composed by comma separated lists of timestamp and measures

The list of the measures, both for the first and second method, must be ordered according to the observed properties order resulted by the *DescribeSensor* request.

Figure 39 - Two examples of how the body of the *fastInsert* request must be formatted.

The *fastInsert* is extremely light and fast because it works directly on the database level. Few controls are developed to validate the request, for example: the procedure id must exist and the single observation must contain as many values as the registered procedure's observed properties. Other data validation, which consume time and resources, are avoided assuming that the sensor are compatible thanks also to the Arduino istSOS library which is described in the next section.

Data transmission (D2S)

The data transmission process is implemented at the Arduino hardware level. Three phases drive the main process:

- the initialization;
- the measuring;
- the communication.

• Figure 40 - Data communication diagram.

The initialization phase verifies and sets the communication device (SIM800), the sensors and the RTC module which is synchronized using a NTP server. Once the initialization is successfully, the measuring phase begins according to the set observations time interval, (generally 5 or 10 minutes). During this process, Arduino reads the values from the sensors

and log them in a temporary log file (*temp_log*) stored on the SD card. When, according to the setting, it's time to transmit the data to the server (communication phase), the system send the values stored in the *temp_log* file. Upon successfully transmission data are moved from the *temp_log* to the *data_log* file, which hosts all the successfully transmitted data. This permits, in case of transmission failure, to recover untransmitted data during the next transmission session.

This implemented communication strategy is data-loss resilient. In fact, if, during a data transmission session, any error occurs, the process restarts from the measuring phase before of retrying. In case of persistent errors (the communication is not successful for a defined maximum number of times) an error message is logged and communication paused until the next session. Using this approach, the sensor data reading is not affected (interrupted) by unsuccessfully data communication tentative and unsent data are stored in a "to be sent" log file (*temp_log*).

The GPRS connection

The GPRS, which physically transmits data to the service layer, is the most power consuming device. Thus, along with secure connection, good performances in terms of energy saving has been particularly addressed.

Figure 41 - SIM800 initialization diagram.

The algorithm for initializing the hardware communication device (SIM800) is illustrated in Figure 41. It starts by checking the module the availability and resetting it. This to override any possible incorrect configuration. Then, the access point parameters are set and the connection to the cell is established. If one of the previous steps fail, coded error messages are raised and logged.

During the sending phase described in the previous section, the process checks if a secure connection (SSL) is required and eventually enable it. After a successfully communication, certified by a success message returned by the server, the hardware device is put in sleep-mode to save energy. If any error occurs, this module is stopped and an error message is thrown.

The logging strategy

In an EMS data are at the bottom of the chain and require an efficient and consistent system to save and protect them from failures and random issues. For this reason, we have developed a strategy that stage data on a SD card in separate areas for measures already sent to the server and still to be sent. According to the data reading time interval (5-10 minutes), data are saved into the storage and then sent to the server according to set session transmission interval (usually 15-30 minutes).

The SD card is structured with three folders: LOG, SLOG and TMP. TMP contains all the file that are yet to be sent to the server. LOG contains all the data that are already sent. SLOG is used to log system information such as errors and other debugging messages.

The logical diagram in Figure 42 shows the developed strategy for data storage. This interface provides a simple functionality, which takes the input data and store them inside a specific file.

Figure 42 - Logging process diagram.

Once data are read from the sensors, they are logged in a file within the TMP folder as a CSV string with sampling time and values:

```

timestamp, measure_1, measure_2, measure_3, ..., measure_i
2017-08-24T12:00:57+0000,36.00,1,3,980.66,50.46,26.69,0.00,135,1.08
  
```

Since big file reading can stress the limited resources of the OpenLog and cause failures, data are stored in smaller chunks by creating one file for each one hour of data. To comply with the OpenLog restrictions, the file name is composed by eight characters (excluding the .TXT extension) is encoded as follows:

- the first character, which must be a letter, is the 'L';
- two characters for the year;
- one character for the month converted to HEX notation;
- two character for the day of the month;
- two character for the hour.

The illustrated strategy permits to automatically synchronize the node with the server, without losing information even in the cases where the communication is not stable.

2.4 4nse-mod prototype system testing

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

To evaluate data quality parameters, a preliminary comparison between the first 4nse-mod prototype and an official weather station, named Trevano has been performed. This comparison tests the data quality and robustness of the system and helps in finding eventual weaknesses. To execute this comparison, the 4nse prototype has been installed closed to the Trevano station (Figure 43) in order to observe the same micro-clima.

The 4nse-mod has been set-up with the whole EMS chain of components, from the hardware to the service and communication layer. Data are sent using the GPRS connection to an istSOS instance installed appositively for the 4nse project where all the future data of the project should merge. The test started at the beginning of July and is still running to collect data that are useful to improve and finalize the system.

The data quality has been evaluated by comparing the time series of the two stations through:

- visual comparison of the recorded data;
- calculation of the coefficient of determination by Pearson;
- coherence of aggregated values (daily mean, max and min values);
- scatter plots to evaluate the general behaviour of the 4nse weather sensors;
- probability density function to validate the accuracy of the values.

Figure 43 - Trevano versus 4nse prototype.

To conduct the data analysis the python library called Observation Analysis Tool (OAT) developed by the IST within the FREEWAT project (www.freewat.eu) has been used and improved. OAT is a timeseries pre- and post-processor tool designed to support modelling (Cannata, et al. 2017). New python scripts have been developed to produce automatic analysis of the data; these scripts can be integrated in the future version of the OAT module.

2.5 4nse-pcb prototype system testing

(B.H. Sudantha, Emeshi Warusavitharana, Sandaru Weerasinghe, Dananjaya Bandara)

The measured data of the 4nse-pcb prototype, installed at the University of Moratowa, was validated with the observations of the nearest high quality weather station. This station acting

as a reference station belongs to the Sri-Lanka Meteorological Department. This station is located approximately 4.5km away from the location of the 4onse-pcb prototype (Figure 44). Table 12 shows the information of the two stations. The 4onse river gauge was not compared with other data at the time of writing.

Figure 44 - Locations of the 4onse system and the reference station belongs to Meteorological Department.

Criterion	4onse-pcb system	Station belongs to the Meteorological Department
Coordinates	4onse-pcb main station - (6.7971°N, 79.9021°E) 4onse-pcb river gauge - (6.7978°N , 79.9040°E)	(6.8167°N, 79.8667°E)
Elevation (from MSL)	4onse-pcb main station – 36m 4onse-pcb river gauge – 6m	9m
Measured parameters during the period of 12 th July 2017 to 25 th August 2017	Temperature, atmospheric pressure, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction, water level	Temperature, atmospheric pressure, relative humidity and rainfall

Measured interval	15 minutes	Temperature and Relative humidity – 1 hour Atmospheric Pressure – 3 hours
Installed location	4onse-pcb main station - At the roof slab (5 th floor) of the Faculty of Information Technology building of University of Moratuwa 4onse-pcb river gauge – At a water body (Bolgoda River) close to the university premises	In an open environment close to the ocean

Table 12 - Information of the 4onse-pcb system and the station belongs to Meteorological Department.

3 Results and discussion

In this chapter the results of the tests and comparisons are discussed and presented for each layer of the system developed.

3.1 4onse-mod test results

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

The weather station prototype development is a milestone in reaching the goal of the project. For this reason, a 4onse-mod prototype has been tested for two months to preliminarily evaluate the quality of the sensors and the general behaviour of the system.

The weather data, produced by the 4onse-mod prototype weather station, has been compared with the time series of an official weather station of the Canton Ticino monitoring network. It is installed in Ticino at the Campus Trevano, Canobbio in Switzerland and measures: air temperature, humidity, pressure and rainfall (see section 0). The time period taken into account spans from the 15 July 2017 to the 10 September 2017.

Temperature

In this paragraph, the results of the temperature data comparison are shown to evaluate the goodness of the DS18B20 which has been chosen as the principal temperature sensor of the 4onse-mod prototype weather station.

In Table 13, the coefficients of determination by Pearson are based on the comparison of the time series values illustrated in Figure 45 (Trevano time series versus 4onse time series). The first graph shows the 4onse and Trevano time series with values aggregated and averaged every ten minutes. The other graphs plot daily maximum, mean and minimum temperature data. The R-squared coefficients is very high for each of the compared time series (Table 13).

A deeper evaluation has been done through the production of scatter plots based on the same time series described above (Figure 46). The scatter plot with ten minutes aggregated time series shows a general good data prediction of the 4onse-mod weather station where values fall inside a 1degree interval. Temperature values between 20 and 30 degrees show more variability and deviation from the identity line. This behaviour is probably due to the summer climatic period in which the data are recorded. This means that the most amount of data falls in this temperature interval and can explain the greater variability present.

Better results can be found with the scatter plots of daily mean and min temperatures where values are general equal for the two stations. A slight trend to overestimate maximum temperature is observable with the comparison of maximum daily temperature which is confirmed by the density probability plots in Figure 47. The density probability plots help to get an evaluation of the residual errors showing very interesting results.

The 95% of the ten minutes aggregated data falls inside a range between -0.2 and 0.5°C which is a very good result and the 5% between -1 and 1°C . Thus, it generally confirmed a trend to overestimate the temperature values of the DS18B20. In addition, very interesting is the analysis of the probability density plots of the daily minimum, mean and maximum values. The first shows a better accuracy than the others and the second shows how the mean error over averaged daily values is around 0.15°C .

The preliminary evaluation performed shows that the sensor chosen and the set-up used fit the requirements of the project in terms of data quality and it is totally acceptable for the purpose of the project.

Figure 45 – Temperature time series overlapping for the 10 minutes aggregated values and maximum, minimum and mean daily values.

Temperature time series	R ²	Mean error
10 minutes aggregated series	0.99	0.15
Daily max temperature series	0.99	0.07
Daily mean temperature series	0.99	0.14
Daily min temperatures series	0.99	0.16

Table 13 - The square of the correlation coefficient between 4onse and the Trevano temperature series.

Figure 46 – Trevano versus 4nse weather station temperature data (10 minutes aggregated and daily maximum, mean and minimum values).

Figure 47 – Probability density function of the residual deviations from the Trevano temperature time series (10 minutes aggregated, daily maximum, mean and minimum values).

Humidity

The same analysis, performed for the temperature parameter, has been done for the humidity values produced by the BME280 sensor. The coefficient of determination of the time series shows, also in this case, very good results with values of 0.99. The high grade of correlation does not underline some small issues which affect the sensor. In fact, scatter plots (Figure 49) report a tendency to underestimate values between 20 and 70% of humidity and to overestimate high values of humidity which are closed to the air water saturation. Daily mean values error is around 4% and minimum values generally show worse results (6% of mean error). This is confirmed by a visual comparison of the time series overlapping in Figure 48. There is an offset of 6% in daily minimum humidity values, on the other hand the daily max values fit better the Trevano trend.

These evaluations are confirmed by the density probability plots (Figure 50) of the residual errors that offer some interesting information. Focusing on the mean values plot, the trend has two peaks one at -6% and another less high at about 1%, additionally the 95% of the data falls between -9% and 2%.

In conclusion the BME280 has a double behaviour but generally it underestimates values and only emphasizes the humidity when the parameter is near the saturation.

Figure 48 – Temperature time series overlapping for the 10 minutes aggregated values and maximum, minimum and mean daily values.

Humidity time series	R ²	Mean error
10 minutes aggregated series	0.99	-4.19
Daily max series	0.99	-1.53
Daily mean series	0.99	-4.21
Daily min series	0.98	-6.16

Table 14 - The square of the correlation coefficient between 4nse and the Trevano humidity series.

Figure 49 – Trevano versus 4nse weather station humidity data (10 minutes aggregated and daily maximum, mean and minimum values).

Figure 50 – Probability density function of the residual deviations from the Trevano humidity time series (10 minutes aggregated, daily maximum, mean and minimum values).

Pressure

The BME280 was mainly chosen because it offers pressure measurements with high accuracy. Unfortunately, the comparison is executed rounding the BME280 pressure values to zero decimals by considering the fact that the Trevano weather station offers this level of precision.

The visual comparison of the time-series in Figure 45, together with the coefficients of determination in Table 15 offers very high values of correlation. The trend of the two series is almost the same and only in some minimum peaks there are little gaps. The scatter plot of the daily mean values illustrates that the pressure data are on the identity line or a little overestimated. Generally the 95% of the errors of the ten minutes averaged, maximum, mean and minimum daily series span respectively over intervals of 0 and 1 hPa, -0.2 and 0.7 hPa and finally -0.4 and 0.6 hPa as shown in the probability density plots (Figure 53).

Figure 51 – Pressure time series overlapping with coefficient of determination.

Pressure time series	R^2	Mean error
10 minutes aggregated series	0.99	0.25
Daily max series	0.99	0.34
Daily mean series	0.99	0.24
Daily min series	0.99	0.19

Table 15 - The square of the correlation coefficient between 4nse and the Trevano pressure series.

Figure 52 – Trevano versus 4nse weather station pressure data (10 minutes aggregated and daily maximum, mean and minimum values).

Figure 53 – Probability density function of the residual deviations from the Trevano pressure time series (10 minutes aggregated, daily maximum, mean and minimum values).

Rain

The precipitation is one of the most important weather parameter. The quantity of rain is useful for flooding and drought events management and for the elaboration of different indexes and climatic analysis.

During the period taken into account, nine rainfall events have been identified from both stations' data analysis (Table 16). According to this table and to the scatter plot in Figure 54, the underlined events show a better performance when the precipitation is under 20 mm. The

error increases with higher values of precipitation: the event number 2 is overestimated of 4.8 mm; the events 3, 6, 7 are similar; the events 1,2,4,5,8 and 9 underestimate the precipitation events of more than 2 mm.

In Table 17, the values of the maximum cumulated rain using two temporal moving windows of 24h and 1h are shown. In this case there is a specular behaviour of the sensor: the maximum value of rain in 24h is overestimated by +5 mm; the maximum value of cumulated rain in 1h is underestimated by -7 mm.

During the test's time period, the total cumulated rain recorded is: 292 mm for the 4onse prototype and 317 mm for the Trevano station, only 25 mm of discard.

On the basis of the calibration process described in the rain gauge paragraph of the section 2.1 and of the illustrated results, the accuracy of the sensor could be improved by a new calibration that takes into account the current lags.

Figure 54 - Rainfall time series graph and scatter plot (4onse vs Trevano).

Event n°	4onse (mm)	Trevano (mm)	Δ (mm)
1	20.2 mm	22.6 mm	-2.4
2	29.8 mm	25.0 mm	+4.8
3	17 mm	16.8 mm	+0.2
4	45.2 mm	49.6 mm	-4.4
5	25.4 mm	27.8 mm	-2.4
6	13.6 mm	13.2 mm	+0.4
7	7.6 mm	7.8 mm	-0.2
8	8.6 mm	10.8 mm	-2.2
9	27.2 mm	32.0 mm	-4.8

Table 16 - Rain discretized events for the reference period.

Rain max	4onse (mm)	Trevano (mm)	Δ (mm)
----------	------------	--------------	---------------

24h	29.8	24.8	+5
1h	57.6	64.6	-7

Table 17 - Comparison of the 1h and 24h rain max.

3.2 4onse-pcb test results

(B.H. Sudantha, Emeshi Warusavitharana, Sandaru Weerasinghe, Dananjaya Bandara)

Reliability

The system has been designed to avoid failures in capturing and sending data. For that purpose, the system is equipped with a durable power supply system (Rechargeable battery of 25Ah and solar panel of 30W) and a 2G GSM communication system. In addition, the system is equipped with an SD memory card to store data temporarily. The system attempts five times to send data sequentially if any failure is registered. This, under the assumption that the chances of failing to send data are extremely infrequent, in fact, there is a high probability that one out of five attempts is successful in sending data to the server.

On 3rd of April 2017, this resilience was tested for 4 hour period after cutting the communication. Throughout this period, the memory card was able to save the readings which were meant to upload to the server. Table 3.2.1 shows the saved data on the memory card with its time stamp.

Recorded Time	Humidity	External Temperature (°C)	Light Intensity (lx)	Wind direction	Pressure (pa)	Soil moisture (%)	Battery Voltage (V)
03-04-17 9:02	49	36	1879	270	100514	46	12
03-04-17 9:17	49	36	1885	225	100533	46	12
03-04-17 9:32	54	34	1726	225	100542	46	12
03-04-17 9:47	56	34	1378	180	100566	46	12
03-04-17 10:02	61	32	1256	270	100561	50	12
03-04-17 10:17	61	32	1285	225	100572	50	12
03-04-17 10:30	61	32	1452	225	100561	50	12
03-04-17 10:45	59	31	1245	180	100559	41	13
03-04-17 11:03	61	29	1573	135	100389	62	12
03-04-17 11:15	61	29	1452	135	100272	61	12
03-04-17 11:31	61	29	1245	90	100266	61	12
03-04-17 11:44	61	29	1235	135	100247	62	12
03-04-17 12:02	60	29	1257	180	100234	62	12

03-04-17 12:15	60	29	1254	270	100219	63	12
03-04-17 12:32	60	29	1483	270	100216	62	12
03-04-17 12:45	60	29	1245	270	100209	61	12

Table 18 - Recorded measurements by the memory chip on 3rd of April 2017.

Data integrity

The prototype system was developed at the system embedded laboratory of Faculty of Information Technology, University of Moratuwa. The laboratory is located at the 4th floor of the faculty building. Due to the convenience of checking the system, the 4nse-pcb main station was installed at the roof slab (5th floor) of the same building. The 4nse-pcb river gauge was installed at the nearest river close to the university premises. Before connecting the system to the istSOS server, the data was uploaded to a private data server at every 15 minutes. The charts given below show the sample of recorded data during the period of 12th July 2017 to 25th August 2017 with reference to temperature, atmospheric pressure, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction and water level. Since some of the sensors were not included to the system during this period, the charts do not represent the recorded information on rainfall, light intensity and soil moisture.

←→ - The system was dismantled during this period for testing purposes

Figure 55 - Temperature - from 12-07-2017 (19:39pm) to 25-08-2017 (16:23pm).

←→ - The system was dismantled during this period for testing purposes

Figure 56 - Atmospheric pressure - from 12-07-2017 (19:39pm) to 25-08-2017 (16:23pm).

← → - The system was dismantled during this period for testing purposes

Figure 57 - Relative humidity - from 12-07-2017 (19:39pm) to 25-08-2017 (16:23pm).

← → - The system was dismantled during this period for testing purposes

Figure 58 - Wind speed - from 12-07-2017 (19:39pm) to 25-08-2017 (16:23pm).

← → - The system was dismantled during this period for testing purposes

Figure 59 - Wind direction - from 12-07-2017 (19:39pm) to 25-08-2017 (16:23pm).

←→ - The system was dismantled during this period for testing purposes

Figure 60 - Water level - from 12-07-2017 (19:39pm) to 25-08-2017 (16:23pm).

Data validation

The common parameters measured by the 4nse-pcb and the nearest weather station of the Meteorological Department were taken for the validation. As shown in Table 12, these common parameters are temperature, relative humidity and atmospheric pressure. The measurements of the 4nse river gauge were not validated due to the unavailability of any nearest reference river gauge. Considering the data continuity of the two stations, the records of the following durations have been taken to validate the each above parameter:

- Temperature – 20th August 2017 09:00 to 21st August 2017 08:00
- Relative humidity – 20th August 2017 01:00 to 20th August 2017 00:00
- Atmospheric Pressure – 19th August 2017 00:00 to 22nd August 2017 03:00

The three charts given below show the temperature, relative humidity and atmospheric pressure records with reference to reference station and 4nse-pcb during the selected time periods.

Figure 61 - Temperature records of Reference station and 4nse-pcb (20th August 2017 09:00 to 21st August 2017 08.00).

Figure 62 - Relative humidity records of Reference station and 4nse-pcb (20th August 2017 01:00 to 20th August 2017 00:00).

Figure 63 - Atmospheric pressure records of Reference station and 4onse (19th August 2017 00:00 to 22nd August 2017 03:00).

To test the goodness of fit between the measurements of the two stations, the Pearson’s correlation coefficient between the reference station’s measurements and the 4onse station’s measurements were calculated.

Parameter	Correlation coefficient	Degree of correlation
Temperature	0.5977	Strong correlation
Relative humidity	0.0826	Small correlation
Atmospheric pressure	0.0249	Small correlation

Table 19 - Pearson’s correlation coefficient values between reference station and 4onse station.

The temperature is affected by altitude, wind, distance from water bodies and surface cover such as vegetation. The reference station and the 4onse-pcb station is located 9m and 36m from MSL respectively. Since the reference station is located in an open coastal environment and the 4onse station is located at the roof slab, the two stations are exposed to wind. Further, the reference station is located 100m away from the ocean and the 4onse-pcb station is located 200m away from Bolgoda River. Accordingly, the two stations are operated relatively in cooling environments. Therefore, the correlation value of the temperature parameter is strong compared to the other two parameters.

The relative humidity is influenced by temperature and geographic location. Areas with lot of surface water has high humidity levels due to evaporation. Since the reference station is located in a coastal environment close to the ocean, it has high humidity levels compared to the 4onse-pcb station. Hence, the correlation value is very low for relative humidity parameter.

Temperature, humidity and altitude are the main factors which influence for atmospheric pressure. Even though the two stations are operated in a relatively cool environment, as

discussed in the previous paragraphs, the humidity levels and the altitudes are completely different at the locations where the two stations are installed. Therefore, the correlation value is very low for atmospheric pressure.

3.3 Service testing results

(M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic)

Here a summary description of the load test's results (see section 0). 100, 200 and 500 concurrent users are simulated to automatically stress the systems with the SOS core requests (*GetCapabilities*, *DescribeSensor* and *GetObservation*).

Load tests results

All the tests presented in the section 0, are run for both VM-0 and PM for about one hour per levels of users simulated. In Figure 64, a general overview of the results are presented.

The first graph shows a better capacity of the PM to solve a higher quantity of SOS requests in the three simulated scenarios. In addition, for higher levels of users the PM increases its performance with better rates. On the other hand, the VM-0 maintains, more or less, the same number of requests solved per hour.

Evaluating the time response of the mandatory SOS requests, the PM strongly increases the performances of the *GetCapabilities* and *GetObservation* respectively by a factor of 564 and 3.24. The impressive result achieved for the *GetCapabilities* request is mainly due to the simple cache system introduced within the istSOS-proxy software.

A different behaviour characterized the results of the *DescribeSensor* request. In general, the time response of this request is always very low because of the intrinsic nature which basically has to retrieve the metadata of the sensor requested. In this context, the istSOS-proxy instead of adding velocity to the system seems to slightly decrease the performances in particular when 500 users are simulated. Even if the differences should not be relevant from a user perspective, the worse results are probably due to the tiny work load added by the software to this very light response.

Figure 64 - From top-left: number of requests, average response time in milliseconds for the *GetCapabilities*, *DescribeSensor* and *GetObservation* with 100, 200 and 500 concurrent users (*Strigaro et al., 2017*).

3.4 Communication testing results

(*M. Cannata, D. Strigaro, M. Cardoso, M. Antonovic*)

The communication testing results regards two analyses performed in order:

- to validate the stability and reliability of the new *fastInsert* method used to transmit data;
- to show the issues encountered during the test period related to the data transmission from the device to the server.

Server statistics results

In order to prove the stability and efficiency of the fast communication developed within the istSOS system the *fastInsert* requests have been monitored during the whole period of the prototype test. For this analysis the time period, taken into account, is the same chosen for the weather parameters comparisons.

6785 is the total number of requests, no failures have been detected. The system did not stop, fail or cause any problems to the communication. The bandwidth used is 2.5 Mb which is useful also to estimate the costs related to the mobile connection. In this case only one prototype is configured to use the *fastInsert* of the 4nse istSOS instance. The presented statistics are representative of the communication between the server and a single station. Thus, data sent by a weather station which measures observations every minute consumes very low bandwidth which corresponds to very low costs for the mobile connection.

The Figure 65 shows the number of the *fastInsert* requests per day. Generally, the same number of request per day is expected to underline a very stable connection and transmission. In Figure 65, the trend is not constant because some minimum and maximum peaks are displayed. These plotted peaks are due to the maintenance and bugfix actions where the communication was disabled. Thanks to the logging strategy, data have been rescued and sent manually to the istSOS trough a script. The manual data insertion is visible looking at the graph on the 11th of September.

Figure 65 - Number of *fastInsert* requests.

Data transmission results

The test performed was useful to find and solve some issues encountered about the data transmission process. In the following table a list of issues and their solutions are shown:

Issue	Solution
The RTC gave a date string with 60 seconds. Thus, the istSOS threw an error because the date is not conformed to the iso8601 format.	A control on the format of the date must be done to avoid failures on the server side.
During a maintenance action the station was powered off occasionally while the system was migrating the data sent from the TMP to the LOG folder. This cause redundancy on the data because when we powered on the system it tried to send data already transmitted to the server.	The istSOS can handle this situation checking and then discarding the values already added without blocking the procedure. In this way the station will move correctly the data from one folder to the other.
The time zone was set to +0000 after removing and replacing the SIM card.	Data are archived without setting the time zone and using the Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). In this way, also

	the issues related to the legal or solar date are solved.
Data transmission failed because of mobile connection stability. This problem is caused due to the possibility the connection can go down. In this situation data are correctly stored in the TMP folder, but when the connection is established the size of the file can be big enough to stress the Arduino.	The solution is to increase the time interval to 5 or 10 minutes in order to have files with less rows. The bottle neck is not correlated to the quantity of files to be sent, but to the size of a single file. In fact, the OpenLog reading big files retrieves an empty string.

3.5 Cost effectiveness of the 4onse system

((B.H. Sudantha, Emeshi Warusavitharana, Sandaru Weerasinghe, Dananjaya Bandara, D. Strigaro)

Table 20 lists the costs incurred in developing the two 4onse prototypes system with a river gauge. The costs have been separately calculated for components of the 4onse-mod and 4onse-pcb main station - main system block, power supply section and sensor unit, mounting and housing items and 4onse-pcb river gauge.

No	Item	Description	Qty	Cost (CHF)
Components of the 4onse-mod system block				
1	Arduino Mega2560	Main controller	01	14
2	DROK Module SIM800	GSM Module for data communication	01	28
3	OpenLog	SD module for data storage	01	15
4	RTC DS3231	To set the time stamp for measured data	01	14
5	DHT11	To measure the system's internal temperature	01	5
6	Step-down converter	To convert the voltage as Arduino and the other components requirements	02	5
Components of the solar power supply of the 4onse-mod solution				
7	Switched-mode power supply	To power up the system	01	15
Sensors of the 4onse-mod weather station				
8	DS18B20*	To measure the temperature	01	7

8	BH1750 Light sensor module	To measure the light intensity	01	13
10	YL-69 Soil moisture module	To measure the soil moisture	01	3
11	BME280*	To measure atmospheric pressure and humidity	01	19
12	Wind speed and direction sensors	To measure the wind speed	01	50
13	6465 Davis AeroCone Rain Gauge with Mountable Base*	To measure the rainfall	01	122
Components required for mounting and housing the main weather station (without pole)				
14	Large size plastic box	Box (300×220×120) – To carry the main processing unit	01	24
15	Miscellaneous	Screws, cables, etc.	01	20
Total cost of the 4nse-mod station				339

No	Item	Description	Qty	Cost (USD)
Components of the main system block (Sri Lanka market reference)				
1	Arduino Mega2560	Main controller	01	10.45
2	SIMCOM SIM800	GSM Module for data communication	01	30.70
3	SD Module	SD module for data storage	01	7.84
4	RTC module with EEPROM	To set the time stamp for measured data	01	0.98
5	16 x 2 Alphanumeric LCD	To display the data in the system	01	2.29
6	DHT11	To measure the system's internal temperature	01	1.63
7	12V DC brushless Fan	For cooling the system	01	1.95
8	Relay module (12V, 5A)	To control the internal fan of the system	01	1.46
9	Printed Circuit Board (PCB)	To connect all the components of the weather station	01	9.18
Components of the power supply section of the main weather station				

10	100W Solar Charger	To charge the battery	01	11.16
11	30W Solar panel	To charge the battery	01	32.84
12	12V, 25Ah rechargeable battery	To power up the system	01	32.84
13	LM338K Voltage regulator	To regulate the power	01	4.90
14	LM7805 Voltage regulator	To regulate the power	02	1.00
Sensors of the main weather station				
15	DS18B20*	To measure the temperature	01	4.91
16	BH1750 Light sensor module	To measure the light intensity	01	3.58
17	Soil moisture module	To measure the soil moisture	01	5.19
18	BME280*	To measure atmospheric pressure and humidity	01	4.90
19	ZHIPU wind speed sensor*	To measure the wind speed	01	55.38
20	Anemometer 485 Wind direction sensor*	To measure the wind direction	01	98.32
21	6465 Davis AeroCone Rain Gauge with Mountable Base*	To measure the rainfall	01	154.85
Components required for mounting and housing the main weather station				
22	Large size plastic box	Box 1 (12"×10"×2") – To carry the main processing unit Box 2 (12"×12"×4")– To carry the power supply unit of the main weather station Box 3 (10"×8"×2") – To carry the sensors	03	31.52
23	Mounting pole	3m height and 25mm diameter To carry the boxes with components of the main weather station	01	65.63
Total cost of the 4nse-pcb main station				573.50
Components of the river gauge				
24	HC-SR04 Ultrasonic sensor	To measure the water level	01	1.58
24	Arduino UNO	Controller	01	6.19

25	APC220 RF data transceivers	To carry out the communication between main station and river gauge	02	32.52
26	10W Solar panel	To charge the battery	01	11.39
27	100W Solar charger	To charge the battery	01	8.14
28	12V, 7Ah rechargeable Battery	To power up the system	01	9.12
29	Serial, 1000m RF transmitters	To transmit the river gauge measurements to the main weather station	01	32.54
30	125mm diameter and 4m height PVC tube	To mount the Ultrasonic HC-SR04 sensor	01	11.39
31	Plastic box	River gauge Box (10"×8"×2") - To carry the components of the river gauge	01	9.19
32	Mounting pole with arms and base	3m height and 25mm diameter To carry the boxes with components of the river gauge	01	26.28
	Miscellaneous	Miscellaneous items		3.27
Total cost of the 4onse-pcb river gauge				151.61
Total cost of the 4onse-pcb system with river gauge				725.13

Table 20 - Cost of items of the 4onse main station and river gauge. Sensors were purchased from both local and international market. Hence, shipping charges were added for the sensors which purchased from the international market. They are marked in asterix mark (*). Table 21 shows the shipping charges incurred for the sensors purchased from the international market.

Sensor	Delivery charges (USD)	Mode of Delivery
DS18B20	-	Free shipping
BME280	-	Free shipping
ZHIPU wind speed sensor	12.31	Standard shipping
Anemometer 485 Wind direction sensor	47.69	Express Mail Service (EMS)
6465 Davis AeroCone Rain Gauge with Mountable Base	65.4	USPS priority mail
Total delivery charges = USD 125.40		

Table 21 - Delivery charges for the sensors purchased from the international market.

According to Table 20, the total approximate cost for building the 4onse-pcb main station is about USD 573.50 including USD 125.40 for delivery charges for some sensors. The cost for

building the 4onse river gauge is about USD 151.61. Hence the total cost of the 4onse-pcb system is about USD 725.13 including USD 125.40 for delivery charges for some sensors. In addition, the total cost of the 4onse.mod prototype is 339 CHF without the pole system. The costs of this version are in CHF because the components were purchased in Switzerland. For this reason

The monthly maintenance cost of the system was approximated as follows:

If an officer was appointed for each weather station, he/she will be paid a monthly salary of USD 100. For communication, an approximate amount of USD 10 has to allocate. Hence the total monthly maintenance cost for each weather station is about USD 110.

The 4onse system was compared with some randomly selected wireless and automatic weather stations in the market which measure similar parameters (Table 22). Although there are varying accuracy levels of the parameters measured by each system, the 4onse system is capable of measuring nine parameters with a relatively low cost.

In Sri Lanka, the hydro-meteorological network coverage is restricted to certain locations of the country due to high installation and maintenance costs. Most of the weather stations in Sri Lanka are manually operated and data is transmitted vocally over the phone. In addition, the Meteorological Department owns 38 Automated Weather Observing Systems which have been installed using funds from the international organizations. According to the discussion had with the officers of the Meteorological Department, the cost of each unit is about USD 65,000. Most of the time, the hardware and software of these stations cannot be adjusted to integrate new parameters (Senevirathna, S. and Jayawickrama, V., 2014). Owing to the above constraints, the 4onse system can be a most promising solution for increasing the hydro-meteorological network density of the country in a cost effective manner.

Measured Parameters & other available features	4onse-mod prototype		4onse-pcb prototype		Vantage Pro Plus Station		MetPak RG Weather Station		Rainwise PORTLOG 805-1018 Portable WS	
	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy	Availability	Accuracy
Rainfall	√	0.2mm	√	0.2mm	√	0.2mm	√	0.2mm	√	0.5mm
Wind speed	√	0.6m/s	√	0.2-0.4m/s	√	12m/s	√	12m/s	√	+0.01m/s
Wind direction	√	10%	√	±3°	√	±3°	√	±3°	√	±3°
Temperature	√	±0.5°C	√	±0.5°C	√	±0.1°C	√	±0.1°C	√	±1°C
Relative humidity	√	±3%	√	±3%	√	±0.8%	√	±0.8%	√	2%
Barometric Pressure	√	±1hPa	√	±1hPa	√	±0.5hPa	√	±0.5hPa	√	±0.5 hPa
Light intensity / Solar radiation	√	1.44 times, Sensor Out / Actual lx	√	1.44 times, Sensor Out / Actual lx	-	-	-	-	√	±5%
Soil moisture	√		√	±2%	-	-	-	-	-	-
River Gauge	-	-	√	±0.5cm	-	-	-	-	-	-
Wireless communication	√		√		√		√		√	
Costs	CHF 339		USD 573.50 (USD 725.13 with river gauge)		USD 1,295.00		USD 2611.20		USD 3,595.00	

Table 22 - Comparison table of costs and accuracy levels of 4onse system and some of the automatic weather stations in the market.

4 Deviation from Work Plan

With respect to the work plan this deliverable has been redacted with about 45 days delay due to several review and report adjustment was needed and ongoing discussion on the sensors to be used, mainly because some sensors were not available on the Sri Lankan market, and its shipping take a considerable amount of time, which is not compatible with a sustainable solution.

5 Conclusions

According to the System Design report the 4onse Environmental Monitoring System (EMS) has been developed and tested during three months.

The system has been implemented in all the three designed layers: hardware, service and communication layer. The first layer has been implemented in two versions, both capable of providing real-time observations of temperature, humidity, pressure, light, wind speed, wind direction and rainfall. In addition, a water level prototype has been built to offer a useful instrument for the future project perspectives and activities which regard hydrological watershed monitoring and analysis. The service layer activities have been focused on the enhancement of istSOS reliability and stability by supporting Big-Data. Load tests have been performed to stress the software and evaluate the proposed scalable solution, named istSOS-proxy, which uses a horizontal scalable technique based on partitioning schemes. In addition, a server with a dedicated istSOS instance has been set-up to provide a unique data management service for all the future project's stations. The last layer has been characterized by the development of fast communication tools based on the GPRS technology, chosen as main transmission media of the prototypes, and of a library to implement the communication strategy of the measurements. This last feature, takes into account a logging procedure to provide high consistency of the data and low possibility of data loss.

On the basis of these developments, different analyses have been performed to validate each element of the chain. By comparing the 4onse prototype with the official weather station located in Trevano, the sensors chosen showed a good accuracy either for the temperature, pressure, humidity and rainfall measurements. In particular, the evaluation of the rain gauge gave good perspective; even better results are expected through a more precise calibration process.

The istSOS-proxy solution performances have been compared with a single istSOS instance using different levels of users and a big dataset of sensors and observations. The adopted solution, which uses a single access point to query a partitioned database over different istSOS instances, strongly increases the performances of the *GetCapabilities* and the *GetObservation* SOS requests in all the cases studied.

As final step, the communication between the weather station and the server has been monitored. The *fastInsert* method developed showed good stability and performances. The bandwidth used to transmit two months of data is very low with a total of 2.5 Mb consumed. The result obtained gave some preliminary directions useful to dimension the costs of the mobile plan. During the test period, some issues came out but appropriate strategies have been taken to tackle them.

In conclusion, the system prototype has been built accordingly to the design proposed in the previous report. In addition, the hardware together with the service and communication layer

have been preliminary tested with very promising results which must be confirmed by the following steps of the project. A number of future works are planned to analyse the system's durability and consistency in selected case study area. More rigorous experiments are required to test the suitability of components in the main processing unit, power supply units and sensors against the fluctuating weather conditions and weather proofing the electrical and electronic units.

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